

A machine learning model to aid in predicting flight trajectory sequencing delays near the arrival airport

Brian Kravitz, Danae Zoe Mitkas, and Martin Durbin
Office of NextGen
Federal Aviation Administration
Washington, DC

Brian.Kravitz@faa.gov, Danae.Mitkas@faa.gov, Martin.Durbin@faa.gov

Abstract— The US Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) manages up to 50,000 flights in the U.S. per day. Airport terminal areas are characterized by high traffic density that can lead to safety issues and excessive delay. Time-Based Flow Management (TBFM) is an automation system used by Air Route Traffic Control Center (ARTCC) and Terminal Radar Approach Control (TRACON) facilities to enable management of the high traffic volume in these congested areas. TBFM generates a schedule based on the aircraft estimated time of arrival, which is then used to calculate airborne delay. The Air Traffic Control System Command Center (ATCSCC) is responsible for ensuring the optimal distribution of delay across the National Airspace System (NAS). Our team developed a metric we call “Sequencing Delay” to assess the level of inefficiency in the terminal area resulting from demand exceeding capacity. This metric is currently computed with post-flight data and used to determine how much delay can be moved earlier in the trajectory, which would reduce fuel burn and emissions. In this paper we explore whether estimating sequencing delay prior to a flight reaching the terminal area could be a viable aid to the ATCSCC using TBFM calculated delay to mitigate delays in advance. Sequencing delay is calculated by subtracting a nominal baseline from the distance flown for each corner post and airport arrival flow. We introduce a machine learning (ML) model to predict the distance an aircraft will fly within a 40 nmi radius, approximating the terminal area of the destination airport. The model can be run using data from different phases of the flight (pre-departure, cruise or top of descent) to enable calculating sequencing delay to aid in modifying flight behavior before reaching the Terminal Area.

Keywords-component; Machine Learning, Neural Network, Trajectory-Based Operations, Flight Metrics, Sequencing Delay, Pre-conditioning, Delay Redistribution

I. INTRODUCTION

As air traffic is growing and the airspace becomes more congested, airborne delays are increasing. Most of these delays are encountered at lower altitudes when the aircraft are approaching the arrival airport, due to radar and runway separation requirements. Congestion due to demand exceeding capacity can cause flights to be vectored while waiting to enter the landing queue.

At the FAA, our continuing mission is to provide the safest, most efficient aerospace in the world. To help accomplish this, the FAA utilizes metering automation systems such as TBFM. TBFM’s core function is to balance air traffic demand with system capacity to ensure the maximum efficient utilization of the NAS by scheduling aircraft within a stream of traffic to reach a defined constraint point at specified times, creating a time-ordered sequence of traffic. TBFM makes calculations of terminal area delay using flight plan, aircraft performance characteristics, wind forecasts, and local adaptations. The delay taken by a flight would be more efficient in terms of fuel burn and operating costs if it could be moved earlier in the flight history by absorbing ground delay or by slowing down en route.

Trajectory-Based Operations (TBO) is a tactical air traffic management (ATM) concept that improves strategic planning of aircraft flows to reduce demand-to-capacity imbalances in the NAS. TBO is reactive to the changes in the dynamic environment that makes up the NAS: unpredictable weather, carrier schedules and reactions, and Air Traffic Control (ATC) interactions. Tactical planning requires not only predictions of trajectories, but also predictions of the interaction between trajectories required to maintain safety requirements [1]. The FAA hopes to fully implement TBO over the next decade through a series of upgrades to the TBFM system and the en route and terminal automation platforms [2].

Though there are congestion issues en route, the most pressing congestion occurs at lower altitudes in the area around arrival airports (referred to as the terminal area). This is problematic due to the impact on ATC workload and excess fuel burn required to maintain safe separation. Previous analysis shows that the distance flown by an aircraft in the terminal area is proportional to the congestion encountered.

Efforts have been made to improve the accuracy of the flight time predictions and calculate the airborne delay. Christien et al. [3] introduce a model to predict delays in the terminal area, five hours in advance. They investigated a Recurrent Neural Network and a Random Forest for the proposed problem. The delay prediction was formed as a classification problem, by binning the delay values into small,

moderate, and large delay classes. Since we are interested in minimizing the amount of delay for each flight, we need a real value output; this requires a regression model. Zhang et al. [4] propose a data-driven approach for predicting the flight time and introduce pressure in the terminal area as an input feature. They conclude that wind speed and direction are essential to predicting flight time in the terminal area. However, the variability of wind makes it difficult to predict in advance. Therefore, we developed a model to predict flown distance rather than flight time, so it does not rely on wind information to make accurate predictions.

For the FAA to take advantage of new tools like ML, we need to start exploring uses and improve our own understanding of its challenges and values. Using ML might provide better solutions to emerging complications and increased congestion. In this paper we introduce an alternative to TBFM’s method of calculating the terminal area airborne delay with a ML model that predicts the distance flown within the terminal area (approximated by a 40 nmi radius around the destination airport). The predicted distances subtracted from a nominal baseline will provide the airborne delay. If presented to controllers, this may aid in their sequencing aircraft to reduce costly terminal delays.

With this information, ATC can pre-condition the arrival stream into the terminal area through departure ground delays and slowing aircraft while en route. Pre-conditioning can efficiently decrease congestion in the terminal area, which will decrease distance flown. Of course, TBO must balance more efficient flow into the arrival stream with the need to maintain enough aircraft in the terminal area so that arrival slots are not missed [1].

Pre-conditioning has another positive impact on the efficiency of the arrival flow: increased Required Navigation Performance (RNP) success rates. An internal FAA study shows that RNP success rates are inversely proportional to the number of aircraft in the terminal area. That is, as the terminal density increases, the success of RNP arrivals decreases. As can be seen in Figure 1, RNP arrivals (the dark blue trajectory traces) traverse a much shorter downwind and will experience significantly less sequencing delay in the terminal area when compared to other trajectories (the red trajectory traces) [5].

Figure 1. RNP routes by airport flow [5]

The dataset used in this study includes arrivals to Denver International Airport (DEN) during 2022. This airport was chosen for its high volume of operations and maturity level of the TBFM deployment.

A. Model Overview

While distance flown in the terminal airspace can be estimated based on designated flight routes, these methods do not account for congestion, weather conditions, airport configuration, and other environmental conditions around the airport. To address these limitations, we train our models to predict aircraft flown distance within a 40 nmi radius of its destination airport using historical metric and system data that includes flight information, airport configuration, and environmental characteristics.

In an effort to develop the best model possible with the available data, we developed an in-house ML library to assist in creating deep learning (DL) multilayer perceptron (MLP) artificial neural networks (ANNs), which was used to create a Deep Neural Network (DNN). This kind of model is able to create connections and gain knowledge based on its input data, instead of making assumptions about the dataset and trying to fit it into existing statistical models. Having fewer restrictions to use, the model affords plenty of flexibility in the modeling, which is one of the benefits of these kinds of ML techniques [6][7][8]. We then compared the performance of this DNN with results from using the popular AutoGluon python library.

1) *In-house ML Library*: Our in-house ML library is essentially a wrapper for TensorFlow that simplifies model development, including architecture selection and training. While still in its early stages, currently supported architectures only include DNN, TabNet [9], and Random Forest (RF). Yet it offers great flexibility in its ability to stack and ensemble these architectures. It is designed to find the best performing model automatically and efficiently with its built-in hyperparameter tuning using Optuna. While it works well with minimal manual configuration, it allows the user to adjust any parameter if desired.

2) *AutoGluon*: AutoGluon is a python library that automates ML tasks with just a few lines of code. It can train high-accuracy ML and deep learning models on image, text, time series, and tabular data. We chose AutoGluon for comparison because it includes a larger selection of models which can help evaluate the performance of our in-house library [10].

II. DATA

A. Trajectory Metrics

Across the NAS, approximately 9 million trajectories per year are analyzed, and metrics are generated describing each flight trajectory for different zones, depicted in Figure 2. The zones begin at the departure airport and reach out to a maximum of 120 nmi. The zones end at the arrival airport and reach out to a

maximum of 250 nmi from the arrival airport. Metrics generated for each zone include distance flown, time in the zone, average altitude, number of level offs, distance in level flight, time in level flight, altitude entering the zone, and altitude exiting the zone. In addition, meta data and derived metrics for each flight are included, such as origin airport, destination airport, aircraft type, wake category, RNP equipage, RNP conformance, missed approach flag, departure runway, arrival runway, downwind or straight-in indicator, weather conditions at the arrival airport (winds, ceiling, visibility), airport meteorological conditions (visual or instrument), airport configuration, and the arrival acceptance rate (AAR).

Figure 2. Trajectory Metric Zones

B. Sequencing Delay

Defining the factors that affect the flown distance is one of the key elements of this model. Understanding the complexity of the airspace and the intricacies of traffic management is the first step towards improving efficiency. Making the airspace more efficient would mean reducing additional distance that an aircraft is required to fly within the 40 nmi radius to enter the arrival queue while maintaining safe separation requirements. Sequencing delay is the difference between the total distance flown and the nominal distance value. The nominal distance is calculated from the 15th percentile trajectory distance for the group of flights entering the 40 nmi circle from a specific direction landing on the same set of parallel runways (Figure 3) [11]. We chose to use the 15th percentile distance because it represents an operationally achievable value and would reduce the delay for a significant majority of the flights [12][13].

Figure 3. Nominal Distance and Sequencing Delay

C. Pressure and Sequencing Delay

Pressure is a measure of congestion in the terminal area. Pressure, a.k.a. Terminal Entry Density, is the number of arriving aircraft in the air and inside of the 40 nmi radius circle when an aircraft crosses the 40 nmi radius circle. The relationship between pressure and sequencing delay at DEN in 2022 is shown in Figure 4. Pressure is denoted on the x-axis, average sequencing delay (the black line) refers to the left y-axis, and number of arrivals at each pressure level (the blue bars) refer to the right y-axis. As can be seen in the figure, sequencing delay increases as pressure increases. Also note the distribution of flights by pressure. The lower 25th percentile is represented by the green background, the upper 25th percentile is represented by the red background, and the 25th to 75th percentile is represented by the blue background.

Figure 4. Sequencing Delay by Pressure Categories

The idea behind TBO is to pre-condition a flight's arrival into the terminal area by implementing tactical delays (both ground and air-borne). This will decrease the number of aircraft inside the terminal area, shifting the pressure curve to the left. As can be seen from the chart, less pressure results in less sequencing delay. To execute this preconditioning efficiently, an estimate of the sequencing delay inside 40 nmi is necessary.

D. Data Preprocessing

While there are many reasons why data preprocessing steps may be performed, it all comes down to ensuring the dataset is in a format suitable for training and evaluating the model; doing so will allow the model to identify patterns. Preprocessing can also be beneficial for achieving better model performance and faster training times. We applied the following types of preprocessing steps before training our model:

- Handling missing data
- Feature engineering
- Dimensionality reduction
- Feature scaling and normalization
- Categorical encoding

1) *Missing Data*: We chose to drop rows with missing values, as there were plenty of samples remaining in the features selected for the model.

2) *Feature Engineering*

a) *Binning*: Ceiling and visibility measurements at an airport come from Meteorological Aerodrome Reports

(METARs) or Automated Weather Observing Systems (AWOS) measurements and tend to be very heavily skewed; The vast majority of measurements indicate clear skies and unlimited visibility. However, during times of low ceiling and/or visibility, the conditions can have a dramatic impact on AAR at the airport, which in turn has a dramatic impact on the sequencing delay that will be encountered by arriving aircraft. To assist the model in understanding the importance of low ceiling/visibility values, we consulted with a former Air Traffic Controller and decided to create bins for each value based upon the ranges seen in Table I. Basically, the bins reflect different meteorological conditions that could exist at an airport: Cat II/III, Instrument Meteorological Conditions (IMC), Marginal Meteorological Conditions (MMC), and Visual Meteorological Conditions (VMC).

TABLE I. BINNING CEILING AND VISIBILITY

Meteorological Conditions	Ceiling (feet)	Visibility (nmi)	Bin Category
Cat II/III	< 200	< 0.25	0
IMC	200 - 1,000	0.25 - 3.0	1
MMC	1,000 - 5,000	3.0 - 7.0	2
VMC	> 5,000	> 7.0	3

b) *Boolean Categorical Features*: Categorical features with two unique categories are transformed to Boolean features. For example, our data contains a field that indicates whether a flight flew a downwind or straight-in arrival. Rather than the categorical values “Downwind” and “Straight-In” this was transformed into a Boolean field that is True if it was a downwind flight, False otherwise [14][15].

3) *Dimensionality Reduction*: One might think that including all available features that are relevant to the target variable is a good idea, but if the data’s dimensionality is too high, it can lead to overfitting as well as an unnecessary excess in training time. Dimensionality reduction techniques like Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or feature selection can help reduce dimensionality,

Our post-flight dataset will initially include relevant, irrelevant, and redundant data, and these will determine the final subset of information that will be used as input to the model. The first two categories are determined by the relationship between each feature and the target variable. Strong relationships indicate the relevant data that will likely impact the model performance. Features with irrelevant information can be removed from the dataset to allow the learning algorithm to operate faster and more effectively. After completing an initial down-selection process using domain expertise, the remaining features were split into two groups based on whether the feature contained numerical or categorical data. A correlation matrix was created for each group of features, using the Pierson correlation coefficient for the numeric data and Cramér’s V for the categorical data. These matrices assist in minimizing the redundant features by

identifying those which are highly correlated. Reducing the total number of features through this process will provide a more robust dataset and will enable the processes to run faster due to reduced dimensionality. However, this stage must be performed carefully without arbitrary removal of features in view of saving time and resources, to avoid removing features important to the model results.

Figure 5. Correlation matrix for the numerical features

4) *Feature Scaling and Normalization*: ML models perform best when input data is standardized. Our in-house ML library leverages Keras from TensorFlow to standardize the distribution of the continuous numeric values using the “Normalization” layer. This layer applies a feature-wise normalization to scale the values into a distribution, centered around zero, by computing the mean and the variance of each feature [14][17].

5) *Categorical Encoding*: ANNs operate on numeric values, therefore any feature containing categorical data must be encoded prior to feeding into the neural network.

String categorical features are represented as strings in the dataset. We use TensorFlow’s Keras “StringLookup” and “CategoryEncoding” layers to multi-hot encode the string categorical data fed into the model. This process maps the set of string input values to integer indices using a vocabulary learned from the unique values of each feature. Since the vocabulary is learned from the data and capped in size, the most frequent values will be used to create the vocabulary, and all other values will be treated as out-of-vocabulary (OOV). The input strings are then converted to their index using the vocabulary, which is an integer. In the example shown in Figure 6, the ‘0’ at the beginning of each list indicates the OOV value.

Figure 6. String Input vocabulary mapping example

In the case of integer categorical features, we use TensorFlow’s Keras “IntegerLookup” and “CategoryEncoding” layers to perform the necessary encodings. These layers map a set of arbitrary integer values to contiguous ranges through a table-based vocabulary lookup. Similar to the string lookup, the vocabularies for integer lookup are learned from the data and will be arranged up to the maximum vocabulary size. In the vocabularies created for the integer categorical inputs of the model, “-1” indicates the OOV value [Figure 7] [17].

Input Values	Encoded Values
Arr-Ceil	[-1, 3, 2, 1, 0]
Arr-Vis	[-1, 2, 0, 3, 1]
CDO	[-1, 0, 1]
RNP	[-1, 0, 1]
Turns	[-1, 0, 1]

Figure 7. Vocabularies of integer categorical inputs

E. Final Set of Inputs

The final set of the input variables, after following all the preprocessing steps, is listed in Tables III, IV and V.

TABLE I. NUMERICAL INPUTS

Altitude at crossing 40	Maximum altitude	Pressure within 40
Origin-Destination great circle distance	Top-of-descent great circle distance	Top-of-descent altitude

TABLE II. STRING CATEGORICAL INPUTS

Carrier	BADA type	Arrival runway
Departure configuration at arrival airport	Wake category	Arrival configuration

TABLE III. INTEGER CATEGORICAL INPUTS

Continuous descent operation indicator	Visibility at arrival airport	Ceilings at arrival airport
RNP with radius-to-fix curves flag*		

F. Model Development

Once the input features are identified, we move on to creating the distance predicting models. We trained an MLP ANN using our in-house ML library, as well as an Ensemble using AutoGluon. We also evaluated the neural network that AutoGluon uses in its ensemble for a fairer comparison to our model-limited in-house library.

1) *In-house ML Library*: We developed an in-house ML library initially to facilitate quick and easy creation of TensorFlow-based DNN models. It can be used for both regression and classification tasks. Over time, however, the library has grown to also include TabNet, RF, ensemble, and stacked models, with many other types planned for future

inclusion. This library gave us the ability to learn and experiment with different ML architectures. It can automatically split and balance data, create and train models with automatic hyperparameter tuning, and optionally save either the best model or all created models to load at a later time. While its default settings will create a good model without requiring any changes, the library offers flexibility and adaptability to the user by having user-adjustable settings.

We used this library to split our dataset by 64% for training, 16% for validation and 20% for testing. The model weights were tuned by the mean absolute error loss function. The number of the model’s total features is equal to the number of the numerical values, added to the number of unique values in each categorical feature, added to the OOV values created in the preprocessing steps.

Hyperparameters [18] are external configuration variables that are used to manage ML model training. There are many hyperparameters that can be configured with an MLP ANN. Hyperparameter tuning is a process in which a search space is defined for the hyperparameters, and many models, each with a different set of hyperparameter values, are trained in order to find the model with the best set of values. Manually choosing the values to search is not feasible to ensure the entire search space is explored. Performing a grid search solves this problem, however if the search space is too large, it will be very inefficient as it continues to examine areas within the search space that will not lead to good results. We used the Optuna python package to perform hyperparameter tuning, as it can prune the search space when it detects an unpromising trial. TABLE IV shows the numeric hyperparameters and their value ranges searched, while TABLE V shows the categorical hyperparameters and their options searched [19].

TABLE IV. NUMERIC HYPERPARAMETERS

Hyperparameter	Min	Max	Log
Optimizer Learning rate	1e-5	1e-1	True
Optimizer Weight decay ¹	0.85	0.99	False
Optimizer Momentum ²	1e-5	1e-1	True
Kernel Regularizer Weight decay	1e-10	1e-3	True
Number of Units per Hidden Layer	4	128	True
Number of Hidden Layers	1	10	False
Use Dropout	0	1	False
Dropout Rate	0.05	0.20	False

TABLE V. CATEGORICAL HYPERPARAMETERS

Hyperparameter	Options
Optimizer	RMSprop, Adam, SGD
Kernel Regularizer	L1, L2, L1L2, None

*Feature only included in Downwind models

While developing the model it was noticed that there were two distinct clusters of predicted values which were determined to be due to having a combined dataset with flights performing a downwind approach and flights arriving straight-in at the airport. Therefore, we decided to create separate distance-models for these two scenarios. A simplified depiction of the architectures for these DNNs are shown in Figure 8, the line connecting two layers represents a fully connected network. The rest of the parameters remained the same.

Figure 8. DNN Model Architectures

2) *AutoGluon Models:* We trained an ensemble model with AutoGluon. Rather than using hyperparameter optimization, AutoGluon models achieve their high performance by training multiple models, bagging the trained models, and stack-ensembling the models. AutoGluon combines cross-validation with bagging, therefore we merged the DNN’s training and validation sets to use as the training set for AutoGluon [10]. AutoGluon uses the combined input data to create many different training/validation sets, and therefore we expect it to be less biased than using a single training/validation set with a specific ratio, as used in the in-house ML model.

One of the models contributing to the ensemble is a FastAI neutral network, which we save as a more direct comparison to our in-house ML model.

Figure 9. AutoGluon Bagging [10]

G. Evaluation Metrics

We chose three main metrics to evaluate the performance of the models: mean absolute error (MAE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), and R-squared (R^2).

1) *Mean Absolute Error:* The MAE metric was selected for evaluating the performance of the distance predicting model, in part because it is easily understood as the value is in the same units as the target variable. The acceptable MAE value range for the model was determined by noting that in our dataset, straight-in flights arriving at DEN average around 290 kts within their final 40 nmi of flight. This equates to traveling on average within this range approximately 4.8 nmi/min. TBFM’s Timeline Graphical User Interface (TGUI) presents the controller a visual timeline of the arrival stream. The TGUI displays the timeline as a vertical strip with a list of scheduled time of arrivals (STAs) on the right and estimated time of arrivals (ETAs) on the left. The timeline contains hash marks with minute granularity, leaving it up to the controller to estimate ETAs within those intervals. Due to the limitations of the TGUI display format, there may be a 30 second error, at worst, between what the controller believes the ETA to be and what the display is showing. Therefore, we conclude that MAE values under 2.4 nmi are acceptable and comparable to the information provided to the controller by the TBFM system. For downwind flights, since the average speed is 314 kts and downwind arrivals fly approximately 50% farther than straight-in arrivals, MAE values under 3.9 are acceptable.

2) *Mean Absolute Percentage Error:* We selected the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) because it gives similar information as the MAE, but rather than the magnitude of the prediction errors, it provides it as a proportion of the actual values. A 2.4 nmi error is equivalent to 6% of the distance, therefore we conclude a MAPE under 6% would be acceptable.

3) *R-Squared:* R^2 was selected as another way to compare the performance of our in-house ML library model with the AutoGluon models.

III. RESULTS

Predictions were made using the in-house library’s DNN and two AutoGluon models, as well as an estimation of TBFM delay for each scenario (straight-in and downwind). We used the same training and test sets for each model. Results presented in this section are based solely on the test sets.

The DNN was trained with a hyperparameters search comprising 500 trials, each configured to train for a maximum of 25 epochs. An early stopping callback that monitored the validation MAE was used to stop training if the MAE did not improve by more than a value of 1 over 3 epochs.

AutoGluon models were trained using the “best_quality” preset with 10 bag folds for bagging of models, 4 bag sets, and 2 stack levels. This resulted in creating 109 total models.

To evaluate model performance we analyzed MAE, MAPE, and R^2 metrics, as well as viewed Predicted vs Actual and Residuals plots for each model. These plots help visualize model prediction errors. We also computed sequencing delay from model predictions and compared with the actual post-flight data and an estimate of TBFM delays.

TBFM does not directly provide delay values, however we can use its STAs and ETAs to compute an estimate of TBFM delay. When a flight crosses the TBFM freeze horizon, the TBFM STA and ETA estimates for the meter fix crossing and runway arrival time are frozen. The difference between the ETAs for these locations is the estimated transit time, and the difference between STAs is the scheduled transit time. Taking the difference between the estimated and scheduled transit times gives us an estimate for TBFM delay.

As previously noted, there is an important relationship between pressure and sequencing delay. Therefore, we must also verify this relationship still holds when calculating sequencing delay from predicted distances.

A. Straight-in Arrival Models

The test set contained 28,783 flights arriving at DEN with a Straight-in approach. The models were used to predict the distance flown within the 40nm.

All three straight-in models performed within acceptable ranges, with the best model being the AutoGluon Ensemble with an MAE of 1.85 [TABLE VI.]. Both DNN models slightly overpredict smaller distances flown and slightly underpredict the distance flown at larger distances, as can be seen in Figure 10. The AutoGluon ensemble model has a more uniform result, as noticed by its better alignment with the $y=x$ line in the Predicted vs. Actual plot and tighter distribution of residuals. Figure 11 shows the relationship between calculated delays and pressure levels. All three models perform great during times of low pressure, while the AutoGluon models continue to accurately predict sequencing delay as pressure increases. TBFM is limited in its ability to accurately measure the level of delay in the terminal area, as seen by the difference between TBFM delay and actual sequencing delay. This can be attributed to the fact that TBFM does not take into account all of the sequencing delay contributing factors.

TABLE VI. DISTANCE MODEL VALIDATION RESULTS

Straight-In Arrivals Distance Flown Model Performance			
Model	MAE	MAPE	R^2
In-house DNN	2.26	4.52	0.26
AutoGluon Ensemble	1.85	3.71	0.47
AutoGluon (DNN)	2.20	4.43	0.34

Figure 10. Result and Residual plots for the three models

Figure 11. Average delay for flights approaching straight-in

B. Downwind Arrival Models

The test set contained 26,239 flights arriving at DEN with a Downwind approach. The models were used to predict the distance flown within the 40 nmi.

All three downwind models performed within acceptable ranges, with the best model being the AutoGluon Ensemble with an MAE of 2.92 [TABLE VII.]. We observed errors in similar areas with all three models, however, the AutoGluon Ensemble performed better at around 70 nmi., as can be seen in

Figure 12. All models have a negative bias in their residuals, with the AutoGluon Ensemble residuals showing a higher concentration of predictions with no error. Figure 13 shows the relationship between predictions with no error. Figure 13 shows the relationship between calculated delays and pressure levels. All three models perform well during times of low pressure, while the AutoGluon models continue to accurately predict sequencing delay as pressure increases. We observed the same limitation of TBFM to accurately measure the level of delay in the terminal area as seen in the straight-in results.

TABLE VII. DISTANCE MODEL VALIDATION RESULTS

Downwind Arrivals Distance Flown Model Performance			
Model	MAE	MAPE	R ²
DNN	3.21	4.42	0.48
AutoGluon Ensemble	2.92	4.11	0.59
AutoGluon DNN	3.19	4.48	0.53

Figure 13. Average delay for flights approaching downwind

C. Sensitivity Analysis

Our terminal area distance predicting models were developed using post-flight data, however when deployed to an operational environment, values for many of the input features, such as the maximum altitude, may change throughout the course of a flight. We ran a sensitivity analysis for each distance model to understand what effect dynamic input features have on model predictions.

Multiple scenarios were run, where each dynamic input feature was perturbed one at a time (shown in Figure 14 (b) and Figure 15 (b) with the individual feature names), and also all dynamic input features were changed at once to see the cumulative effect of many mispredictions (shown in Figure 14 (b) and Figure 15 (b) with the label “All features”).

Five scenarios were run for the numeric features, where the data was modified up to a maximum proportion of the original value. The modification randomly increased or decreased (with a 50/50 chance) the values up to the maximum proportion. In the first scenario a modest 5% of the original value was changed followed in increments of 5%, all the way up to a significant error of 25% in the last scenario (shown in Figure 14 (a) and Figure 15 (a) in the legend and Figure 14 (b) and Figure 15 (b) in the x-axis).

For numeric categorical features, five additional scenarios were run, where data sensitivity was assessed by modifying a proportion of the data by randomly increasing or decreasing the encoded value (with a 50/50 chance). If the modification creates a value outside of the feature vocabulary, the encoded value is changed in the other direction (i.e. decrease instead of increase) to a valid value. Since our numeric categorical data is ordered, changing the value to a neighboring encoded value assigns realistic error to the data. For example, in the case of the arrival ceiling feature, we wouldn't assign the category for clear skies to replace low ceilings, but rather we'd be assigning the category for the next higher level of ceilings. We do this for each scenario, first with 5% of the values changed, all the way up to 25% of the values changed, by increments of 5%.

The string categorical features in our model (Arrival Configuration, Departure Configuration, and Arrival Runway) all relate to airport runways. For these features, five new

Figure 12. Result and Residual plots for the three models

scenarios were created that select a proportion of the data (from 10% to 50% in increments of 10), wherein half of the values chosen were randomly selected from the same set of parallel runways (airport flow) as the original value and the other half were selected from the opposite airport flow of the original value. In each case we ensure the Arrival Runway is assigned to the same flow as the Arrival Configuration.

1) *Straight-in model sensitivity results:* In Figure 14 (a) the peaks are close to zero and slightly negative representing a small underprediction of straight-in distance flown when error is introduced in the input features. 93% of the predictions with the least amount of perturbation (5%) still remain within the acceptable range of 2.4 nmi, represented by the region within the black dashed lines. In the extreme scenario where all features are perturbed the most (25%), the proportion of predictions within the acceptable range drops to 53%.

(a) Error induced with all features perturbed

(b) Error induced with perturbed data by feature

Figure 14. Sensitivity analysis for flights approaching Straight-In

In Figure 14 (b) most of the features follow the same trend where the average error in distance prediction grows as the amount of error induced in each feature increases. However, the average error in distance prediction remains low, between -0.4 and 1 nmi.

2) *Downwind model sensitivity results:* In Figure 15 (a) 97% of the predictions with the least amount of perturbation (5%) remain within the acceptable range of 3.9 nmi. In the scenario where all features are perturbed the most (25%) the proportion of predictions within the acceptable range drops to 77%, which is significantly higher than the straight-in model. Of note, increasing the amount of induced error in the input features does not seem to influence the predictions that are outside the lower limit of the acceptable range.

In Figure 15 (b) all of the features follow the same trend where the average error in distance prediction grows as the amount of error induced in each feature increases. The average error in downwind distance prediction remains low, between -1 and 2.5 nmi.

(a) Error induced with all features perturbed

(b) Error induced with perturbed data by feature

Figure 15. Sensitivity analysis for flights approaching Downwind

D. Results summary

We are extremely satisfied with the results. The models created perform well for both straight-in and downwind arrivals and can accurately predict sequencing delay within the 40 nmi region around DEN. This has the potential to aid controllers in their sequencing of aircraft when attempting to reduce delays.

Our sensitivity analysis provides confidence that both the straight-in and downwind models are resilient to input errors. This is important because many of our input features are dynamic and will change throughout the course of the flight. Additionally, it defines the performance requirements for individual input models to be developed.

IV. FUTURE WORK

A. *In-house ML Library Enhancements*

Our in-house ML library performed fairly well despite its limited selection of models available for stacking and bagging. Given that the AutoGluon models performed better, we intend to explore the benefit of upgrading the in-house model to include a more robust collection.

B. *Making earlier predictions*

The ability to predict distance flown in the terminal area, and as a byproduct, the estimated sequencing delay post-flight is not the final aim for our research. We intend to use these ML models as a tool to predict expected delays during any phase of the flight trajectory (e.g., Pre-flight, Cruise, Top-of-Descent etc.). Some model input parameters are static and known at all times, such as the Origin-Destination great circle distance, carrier, BADA type, and wake category. The other parameters are all dynamic in nature and are likely to change over the course of the flight (e.g., max altitude, top-of-descent, pressure, arrival corner post, etc.). Some, such as the arrival runway, is not known until the flight is close to the destination. Therefore, to use our model at any time, we will have to estimate what these dynamic inputs are most likely to be. As a flight progresses, the model inputs are expected to change as new updated estimates (e.g., ceilings at arrival runway) or actual data (e.g., top-of-descent great circle distance after the flight starts its final descent), which will lead to new and more accurate model predictions. At any given time, we will be using a different mix of predicted and actual data as input to the model based on the location of each flight.

The next stage of this work will consist of developing models for the dynamic input parameters and evaluating the accuracy of the distance models at all stages of flight: pre-flight, top-of-ascent, cruise, top-of-descent, and entry into the terminal area of the arrival airport. The results of this evaluation will drive our path forward – whether the dynamic parameter input models have merit or if we should pursue more classical physics-based models. Problematic models may require further discussion with Subject Matter Experts to determine the course of improvement.

The full list of input-models that will be developed for use in the distance predicting model is below:

- Final arrival fix
- Arrival airport arrival runway configuration
- Arrival airport departure runway configuration
- Arrival runway
- Top-of-descent altitude

- 40 nmi crossing altitude
- Projected runway turn indicator
- RNP conformance indicator
- Called arrival rate
- Arrival airport buffer

Ideally, these models will be built avoiding features that need to be predicted as much as possible to achieve higher accuracy and more consistent results. However, for some of these models, such as the RNP Usage Indicator, which relies on knowing the Arrival Runway, this may be unavoidable.

C. *Expanding to additional airports*

As previously mentioned, DEN airport was chosen for the initial development of the models because of its high volume of operations and maturity level of the TBFM deployment. Having achieved promising results with DEN we are ready to move forward to develop similar models for other airports with TBFM deployment.

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